

The Enhancement of Student's Organizational Citizenship Behavior to Improve Organizational Embeddedness: An Action Research on Beijing Polytechnic in Beijing, China

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Abstract:- This action research aims to enhance students' organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) to improve organizational embeddedness and reduce future turnover intention in a vocational college. The sample size of this research was 59 sophomore students, 30 in the experimental group and 29 in the control group. They came from Beijing Polytechnic, majoring in mechanical and electrical engineering (MEE). This study's questionnaire instrument has 24 items, the Cronbach alpha reliability test result was 0.887, and the IOC content validity test result was more significant than 0.6 for each item. After the 16-weeks-intervention program, the pre-intervention and post-intervention data were collected. The researcher used the quantitative method. In the quantitative analysis, the researcher used the Shapiro-Wilk (S-W) test, with varied data being non-parametrically distributed. The study findings are: (H1_a) The Spearman's test was applied, and the correlation coefficient $r=0.741$ (0.7 is acceptable), so there is a statistically significant relationship between OCB and organizational embeddedness. (H2_a) The Wilcoxon signed-rank sum test was applied, and all results were $p<0.05$, so there is a statistically significant difference in OCB and organizational embeddedness before and after ODI. (H3_a) The Mann-Whitney U test was applied, $p=0.014<0.05$, so the effect of OCB on organizational embeddedness was statistical significance. The qualitative analysis's findings supported the alternative hypotheses (i.e., H1_a, H2_a, and H3_a). The study concluded that after ODI, participants' OCB level and organizational embeddedness increased, which can also be considered that future turnover intention decreased. The researcher suggested that further studies should continue monitoring these participants' actual turnover behavior when working in the workplace.

Keywords:- Higher Vocational College Graduates, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Organizational Embeddedness.

I. INTRODUCTIONS

Vocational college graduates' turnover has become a vital employment relationship for employees and employers in China. According to the "Chinese 3-year Vocational College Graduates' Employment Annual Report (2020), between 2015 and 2019, the turnover rate of Chinese higher vocational college graduates on the first job within six months of their employment was in the range between 42% and 43%^[1]. But according to the "Government Work Report," in March 2021, 11.86 million new jobs were created in 2020, and the unemployment rate was only 5.6%. Why do vocational graduates have such a high turnover rate? Zhang analyzed in 2019^[2]. He found many concerns in the employment character traits of higher vocational students, such as responsibility, loyalty, and civic morality. There were many shortcomings in employability, such as a lack of teamwork and innovation ability. At the same time, the continuously growing Chinese economy and improving employment policies have enabled employees to have better employment opportunities and be willing to leave for better positions with better benefits and a better career.

The researcher conducted a questionnaire survey of the human resources departments of over 20 companies in the Beijing Economic-Technological Development Area, revealing that about 30% of vocational graduates chose to leave their positions within six months of their employment in the past three years. The adverse effects of the turnover of vocational graduates on the organization are mainly as follows. First, they need to recruit similar personnel to fill the position in time, which causes high replacement costs, and the employers may not be able to find a suitable person in a short time. Second, the high turnover of the new employees will lead to low morale among the remaining employees, significantly affecting the organization's cohesion. Third, most vocational graduates possess specific specialized skills. Therefore, the high employee turnover rate will bring productivity losses.

Vocational education is a kind of education that has the goal of employment. Therefore, employment is one of the essential indicators to test the effectiveness of higher vocational colleges. Governments and administrations at all levels also examine students' employment status upon graduation as a critical performance of the vocational college. And vocational college, as the last stop before

students enter the organization, has an important social responsibility to improve graduates' employment. Vocational colleges are not only responsible for ensuring the employment rate of students but also train students to stay employed longer and thus reducing the occurrence of turnover behavior while they are hired. But for a long time, government and higher vocational colleges have paid almost all their attention to the employment situation of students when they leave school, and not enough attention is delivered to students' job attitude and job stability. As a result, the employment rate of Chinese vocational college graduates is very high, almost always above 90%, but with insufficient job stability and a high turnover rate within six months. This will cause losses to employees and employers. So, figuring out how to cut down on the number of people who leave their first jobs within six months of graduating from a higher vocational college is a big challenge.

Organization citizenship behaviors (OCB) in the theory of OB chart the course for us. The theory of OCB that emerged against the background of industrial and commercial enterprises has attracted much attention since it was introduced into the field of education. Still, most of the research has focused on teachers' OCB. Currently, the research on OCB of higher vocational college students is still in its infancy and is not systematic. Higher vocational college teachers lack experience in organizational operations and practices. For the reasons above, colleges, significantly higher vocational colleges, should integrate cultivating OCB into teaching and conducting interventions to improve students' OCB levels before they graduate, such as combining social reality and simulating workplace context to accommodate different dimensions of OCB learning and training.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Concepts and Definition of OCB

In organizational behavior theory, a higher level of OCB can help build a better work attitude for the employees, making them more involved, loyal, and conscientious [3]. OCB means that an individual's behavior is relatively discretionary and contributes to the effective functioning of organizations [4]. Anthony et al. developed a profile model which includes five types of OCB (conscientiousness, sportsmanship, civic virtue, courtesy, and altruism) to research the nature, causes, and consequences of profiles of OCB [5]. They tested whether employees engaged in discernible and predictable patterns of citizenship behavior, and the shapes yielded significant value in understanding multidimensional behavioral constructs. They provided evidence that citizenship profiles differ both quantitatively and qualitatively, and certain citizenship motives would influence employees' profiles of OCB.

Meanwhile, citizenship profiles affected employees' job performance ratings, workplace status, and citizenship fatigue levels. Anthony et al. suggested that managers should understand the different patterns of citizenship in their organizations and identify the patterns of OCB. Employees tend to express and attempt to place themselves in roles that, in Anthony's view, are most valuable.

Through the literature above and the description of OCB research in China in Chapter 1, the researcher found that different scholars have given different definitions in the study of OCB. For example, Farh gave 10 dimensions of OCB [6], and Anthony et al. developed five types of OCB models. These definitions, which are based on different cultural backgrounds and research directions, are separate but will contain some standard dimensions, such as responsibility, civic virtue, etc. In this study, the intervention subjects are vocational college students, and the intervention is conducted by simulating a work scenario in an organization, so the researcher combined the above commonalities in the definition of OCB and selected four dimensions to study the OCB behavior of the intervention subjects, including civic virtue, conscientiousness, organizational Identification, sportsmanship. Organizational Identification is defined as the perceived unity and emotional affiliation to an organization. Conscientiousness means the quality of wishing to do one's work or duty well and thoroughly, such as working hard. Sportsmanship means fair and generous behavior or treatment of others, especially in a sports contest, such as being positive at work even when times are tough [7]. Civic Virtue: Individuals have a duty to their communities and societies that they should place above their own desires, such as engaging in the organization's life [8].

B. Concepts and Definition of Turnover Intention

As we all know, attitude determines behavior. The individual must change his or her attitude before taking action. The same is valid for turnover. An individual must have a turnover intention before having turnover behavior. Since it is challenging to use individuals who have already had turnover behavior as the research sample in action research, the study of individual turnover intention is significant. The organization's success is increasingly dependent on key employees in the current changing environment. Therefore, how to retain key employees is a crucial issue. Previous research on employee turnover shows that job satisfaction plays an essential role in turnover [9].

The managers of the organization can perceive not all turnover intentions. And the turnover intention cannot be accurately measured. However, many theories work well on turnover intentions. Previous research on employee turnover shows that job satisfaction plays an essential role in turnover [10]. Chen et al. pointed out three limitations to this research. First, the previous study didn't explain well why, how, and when job satisfaction change influenced turnover intention. Second, the previous research didn't grasp the dynamic nature of job satisfaction and turnover. Finally, the previous study only focused on newcomers. Chen et al. integrated several theories to build a new model that relates job satisfaction changes to turnover intentions. The data for this model was collected from different work settings, types of organizations, and tenure [11]. The results of this study gave a more precise explanation of how, why, and when the change in job satisfaction relates to turnover intention change and, for the first time, identified the boundary condition in tenure. Tschopp et al. examined the impact of career orientation on the static and dynamic relationships between job satisfaction and turnover intention [12].

When studying problems in the organizational environment, Scholars have discovered that job performance, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover intentions are constituents of the role process. Most of these studies focused on the supervisor-subordinate exchange, which was the leader-member exchange (LMX) theory. In recent years, organizational structures have become more abundant^[13], and scholars^[14] have paid more attention to research on the quality of social communication within work groups as described by the team-member exchange (TMX) theory^[15].

C. Concepts and Definition of Organizational Embeddedness

For organizations, integrating key employees is very important, partly because the costs associated with hiring, selecting, and training new employees may exceed 100% of the annual salary for the position^[16]. While traditional theories tend to focus on negative work as the main reason for turnover behaviors, the embedded theory focuses the research on how to keep employees in the organization^[17]. The job embeddedness construct is based on the ideas of embedded figures and field theory. Embedded figures used in a psychological test are images that are immersed in their surroundings and difficult to visually separate from these backgrounds^[18]. The empirical study findings are consistent with the theoretical research, indicating that employees with higher job embeddedness are less likely to leave the organization. In recent years, based on the embedded theory, scholars have shifted the research from why people leave the organization to how it can retain their talents^[19]. The embedded theory describes the factors that prevent employees from leaving the organization, including a person-job and person-organization fit, links with colleagues and work activities, and potential sacrifices associated with changes in employment. More and more empirical studies have also proved that employees with a high degree of job embedding have a lower turnover intention and lower turnover behavior^[20]. The study by Avey et al. also demonstrated that the relationship between abusive supervision and job frustration was moderated by job embeddedness. The relationship was weaker and negative for those higher in job embeddedness^[21].

Then, Peltokorpi et al. extended the job embedding theory. They proposed that employees could be embedded in different ways and that they could also respond to the embedded perception in different ways^[22]. Some scholars have also proposed that the theoretical development of job embeddedness depends on the exploration of moderators, which explains the conditions that embeddedness is more or less related to turnover. Peltokorpi et al. used demographic characteristics, age and gender, value orientations, individualism, and risk aversion as moderators and researched how they moderated the relationship between embeddedness and turnover intentions. Individual demographics and traits^[23] have essential roles in turnover because they affect the value placed on connections in a specific environment and the evaluation of the risks associated with severing ties. Peltokorpi et al. found that gender and risk aversion had a significant interaction between embedding and turnover intention and indirectly

affected voluntary turnover behavior. In contrast, age and individualism had a minor moderating effect. And the embeddedness of the organization could predict turnover intention and voluntary turnover behavior.

The research on job embeddedness in China started a little later than in the West, around 2005. Chinese scholars have validated the content based on Western research for the Chinese context and proposed the connotation, dimensions, and content of job embeddedness in the Chinese context. Chinese scholars define organizational embeddedness as internal embeddedness, part of job embeddedness. Organizational embeddedness is divided into three dimensions: fit, link, and sacrifice, consistent with the West. Yang et al. believe that job embeddedness breaks through the traditional theoretical separation framework and can more effectively predict and explain employee separation behavior^[24]. Wang et al. confirmed that organizational embeddedness has a significant negative effect on turnover intention, further indicating that the deeper the organizational embeddedness of employees, the lower turnover intention^[25]. Several empirical studies by other Chinese scholars with a sample of Chinese employees have also validated the effect of organizational embeddedness on turnover intentions^{[26][27]}. Several empirical studies in China have demonstrated that organizational embeddedness is significantly and negatively related to turnover intentions, and when organizational embeddedness increases, turnover intentions decrease substantially^[28]. Since the intervention subjects in this study were school students and the researcher could measure turnover intentions in a simulated workplace context at college, based on Chinese researcher's studies about turnover intention related to organizational embeddedness. The researcher measures the changes in organizational embeddedness to understand the turnover intention situation. In addition, since the survey of organizational embeddedness was conducted in the colleges' simulated workplace context, so sacrifice dimension of organizational embeddedness was not measured. The research only estimates the changes in the fit and link dimensions. In line with Ng and Feldman, the researcher uses the terms "job embeddedness" and "organizational embeddedness" synonymously in this study because most employees who are embedded in their jobs are also embedded in their organizations^[29].

D. Conceptual Framework of the Study

The researcher designed the conceptual framework as shown in Figure 1. The independent variable is OCB, and the dependent variable is organizational embeddedness. The researcher studies the impact of college OD intervention on graduates' organizational embeddedness based on the changes in the OCB of the research samples in BP simulated workplace context before and after the intervention and then obtains the difference in turnover intention. Hayton et al. and Anthony et al. concluded that intervening with OCB can reduce turnover intention, and Allen & Shanock interfered with OCB and increased organizational embeddedness.

In this action research, the independent variable is OCB, composed of four sub-variables: organizational Identification, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, and civic

virtue. Since the subjects of this action research are students in BP, some variables cannot be observed as intervention results, such as job performance. Therefore, the researcher selected the above four variables as independent variables. In these independent variables, organizational Identification means the degree to which a person and an organization

share values, goals, and aspirations. Conscientiousness denotes a tendency to be self-disciplined, responsible, and achievement-oriented. Sportsmanship refers to being positive at work even when times are tough. Finally, civic virtue signifies engaging in the life of the organization.

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

The dependent variable of this study is organizational embeddedness, including two sub-variables, fit to organization and link to the organization. There are several variables for turnover intention. Since this study is conducted in BP simulating an actual work context, among these variables, well-being, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment must be measured in real-world job positions, which are difficult to simulate in college. In contrast, in the third grade, career orientation is a course offered by BP. Therefore, precise observations were also unavailable for the study's sophomore participants. Based on Mitchell et al., organizational embeddedness includes three core parts: link, fit, and sacrifice. "Link" is the formal or informal connection between an individual and other activities. "Link" to an organization focused on the participant's working groups, relationships with colleagues, and social responsibility in the organization's name. "Fit" means the similarity between the organization where the individual is located and lives. "Fit" to an organization focused on whether the participant shares the organization's values. Finally, sacrifice means the sacrifices or losses individuals face when they leave the organization or community, including material and psychological losses. In this action research, researcher only focus on fit and link because the research objects are students in BP, and it is impossible to simulate the sacrifice scene.

In addition, many Chinese scholars studied organizational embeddedness significantly and negatively related to turnover intention; Yang et al. indicated that when organizational inwardness increases, intention to leave decreases especially. When looking at the turnover intention, organizational embeddedness is used as a sub-variable of turnover intention.

E. Research Hypothesis

The following research hypotheses are used to define the research questions and objectives.

- H1₀: There is no statistically significant relationship between OCB and organizational embeddedness.
- H1_a: There is a statistically significant relationship between OCB and organizational embeddedness.
- H2₀: There is no statistically significant between OCB and organizational embeddedness before and after ODI.
- H2_a: There is a statistically significant between OCB and organizational embeddedness before and after ODI.
- H3₀: The OCB has no statistically significant impact on organizational embeddedness.
- H3_a: The OCB has a statistically significant impact on organizational embeddedness.

III. METHOD

A. Subjects

Participants in this study are students from Beijing Polytechnic (BP). BP is a higher vocational college of three-year education. The subject of the study is a randomly selected two classes of roughly sixty sophomores majoring in Mechanical and Electrical Engineering (MEE). Because the Focal School's turnover rate of MEE graduates is close to the average turnover rate in the past 5 years publicized in the blue book of 2020, so the researcher chooses MEE. Compared to freshmen and juniors, the researcher has enough time to conduct OD Intervention for sophomores. So, the researcher decides on sophomores as the subject of this study.

After entering BP, students are divided into different classes according to their majors. Class size is various, between 26 and 32 students each. The classification is randomly arranged by computer. The researcher is not disclosing any information about this study to the Division of Teaching Affairs in advance. Therefore, the researcher requests and receives two sophomore classes to conduct research studies. The researcher randomly selected one of the two classes as the experimental group and the other class as the control group. The experimental group had 30 participants, and the control group had 29 participants.

B. Data Collecting Method

Because this study adopts the pragmatism view and the action research methodology, a quantitative method is adopted in data collection and analysis, such as questionnaire surveys. Since this research is to reform the curriculum in the college, it is imperative to get the college's support and the organization's help for smooth data collection. Before the action research starts, the guiding coalition is formed by stakeholders, including HR managers,

teachers, etc., and the support and resources for research and investigation are obtained through communication between the coalition members. The researcher used a quantitative method to collect data from participants through questionnaires. Using a structured questionnaire, the changes in two variables, including six sub-variables, are measured before and after the intervention, including organizational Identification, sportsmanship, civic virtue, conscientiousness, fit to the organization, and link to the organization, with a Likert five-scale for measurement, including 24 questions associated with two variables, as shown in Table 1.

The researcher introduces the purpose and significance of the research to the participants in the class and asks them to complete all the questionnaires because it is the source of diagnosis for developing OD interventions, and the researcher guarantees the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants' answers. SPSS analyses the data collected by the researcher to check for errors. The students' organizational Identification, sportsmanship, civic virtue, and conscientiousness status before ODI are recorded.

	Variables	Number of Questions
OCB	Organizational Identification	4
	Conscientiousness	4
	Sportsmanship	4
	Civic Virtue	4
Organizational Embeddedness	Fit to Organization	4
	Link to Organization	4
	Total	24

Table 1: The Structure of the Questionnaire

Before the intervention begins, all instruments are checked for their reliability and validity. For validity, the researcher makes an item objective congruence (IOC). The researcher invites five experts to participate in the IOC test, including two from the United States with a professorship in the field of OD and the remaining three from China, who are engaged in research on the employment of higher vocational students and students psychology. The results show that the validity of each item in the questionnaire is either equal to or greater than 0.6. Therefore, the questionnaire is valid. For reliability, the researcher uses the Cochran equation to calculate. For finite population, $Sample\ size = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{(n_0 - 1)}{N}}$ = 171, and $n_0 = \frac{Z^2 p(1-p)}{e^2}$. In the equation, N is the population size. The researcher selects students from the Mechanical and Electrical Engineering School of Beijing Polytechnic as the population. The size number is 1415; Z is the Z score, and the Z score for a 95% confidence level is 1.96; e is the margin of error, the researcher chooses a margin error of 4%; p is the Standard deviation, the researcher decides to be 0.2. According to this formula, the researcher makes a pre-test. A total of 210 questionnaires were requested, among which 205 questionnaires were valid responses. The Cronbach's α is 0.887. The results show that the questionnaire is reliable.

C. Data Analysis Method

In quantitative analysis, SPSS is used to evaluate data on variables. First, check whether the data conforms to a normal distribution. The mean is used to measure and compare each variable's improvement before and after the intervention. The mean and standard deviation are used to show major trends and data comparisons. To interpret the information more efficiently, demographic data is measured using percentages. The Wilcoxon sign rank test is used to test the significant difference in the paired samples in the experimental group and control group. The Spearman's test is used to calculate the strength of the relationship between variables. The Mann-Whitney U test significantly differentiates between Pre- and Post-ODI in a different group.

D. OD Intervention Model

The researcher develops an OD intervention model with the guiding coalition. Then, the researcher intervenes in courses to improve participants' OCB levels. Since the participants are all college students, they may not directly understand the researcher's intentions when measuring their turnover intention. The researcher measures students' organizational embeddedness in a simulated work context questionnaire. This is an innovative design not previously available and an appropriate means of measuring students' future turnover intention in the organization. When the level

of organizational embeddedness increased, students' future turnover intention decreased.

In the course, the researcher simulated the future work context of the students once they enter the organization. The first step was to achieve an identity shift. The intervention subjects changed from a classmate to a colleague relationship, the class switched to an organization, and the work groups were randomly generated. The researcher will work with the significant course instructor to distribute the learning content as a project and have the students complete it in a workgroup. For example, a project task was given to complete a circuit design to implement a specific function. Intervention subjects were randomly assigned to work groups to experience the same work and interpersonal patterns as in the future organization. After completing the project, the issues have a presentation about the project and complete a questionnaire as an employee to evaluate themselves, their "colleagues," and their "organization" from the employee's perspective. Interventions can be categorized into improving students' organizational identification levels and sportsmanship, civic virtue level, and conscientiousness. On the other hand, such an intervention model is conducive to enhancing students' future interpersonal skills with employers and colleagues.

The researcher developed an intervention plan where the intervention lasted for 16 weeks, once a week for 2 hours, with different intervention methods in the same strand for various subject awakening interventions. Based on the theories of reinforcement, expectations, and social learning, researcher develop intervention methods like interactive lectures, group discussions, training in soft skills, and role-playing.

IV. ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION AND FINDINGS OF THE DATA

A. Demographic Profile of Participants

59 sophomores participated in this action research, 30 in the experimental group and 29 in the control group. Demographic data consists of age, gender, and work experience. Most participants (more than 76%) are aged between 19 and 20 years old. The second-largest age group is those over 20, who comprise more than 13% of the total participants. Most of these participants have military service experience. Less than 7% of the full participants are younger than 19 years old. Because all participants are majoring in mechanical and electrical engineering (MEE), most of them are male, more than 93% and only 6.67% of the total are female, meaning that there are 2 females out of 30 in the experimental group. Similarly, in the control group, nearly 90% of the participants are male, and 10.34% of the total are female, meaning that there are 3 females out of 29 in the control group. More than half of the participants had work experience, including 17 of 30 in the experimental group and 15 of 29 in the control group. Through interviews, it is learned that their work experience was mainly part-time jobs in the service industry, such as Starbucks and KFC.

B. Tests of Normality

In the pre-ODI stage, the experimental group sent out 30 questionnaires and returned 30, while the control group sent out 29 questionnaires and returned 29. In the post-ODI stage, 30 questionnaires were sent out in the experimental group, 26 were returned, while 29 questionnaires were sent out in the control group, and 29 were returned. To determine the method of data analysis, the researcher first tested whether the data conformed to a normal distribution. The two sets of data were analyzed using SPSS software. In this research, the sample size=24, so the researcher used Shapiro-Wilk (*S-W*) test. In the experimental group, the significance level was $p=0.003$ in the pre-ODI stage and $p=0.001$ in the post-ODI stage. In the control group, $p=0$ both in the pre-ODI and post-ODI stages. Under the test level of $\alpha=0.05$, $p<0.05$, the data does not conform to the normal distribution and requires the use of the non-parametric test for data analysis.

C. Quantitative Analysis of Research Variables in Experimental Group

a) Organizational Identification

Organizational Identification was measured with four items. The response options range from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree). In the experimental group, the overall mean scores on "organizational identification" were 3.16 in the pre-ODI stage and 3.60 in the post-ODI stage. In the Control Group, the overall mean scores were 3.10 in pre-ODI and 3.51 in post-ODI.

b) Conscientiousness

Conscientiousness was measured with four items. In the experimental group, the overall mean score on "conscientiousness" was 3.185 in the pre-ODI stage and 3.58 in the post-ODI stage. In the Control Group, the overall mean scores were 2.975 in the pre-ODI stage and 3.225 in the post-ODI stage.

c) Sportsmanship

Sportsmanship was measured with four items. In the experimental group, the overall mean score on "sportsmanship" was 3.15 in the pre-ODI stage and 3.32 in the post-ODI stage. In the Control Group, the overall mean scores were 3.24 in the pre-ODI stage and 3.32 in the post-ODI stage.

d) Civic Virtue

Civic virtue was measured with four items. In the experimental group, the overall mean score on "civic virtue" was 3.25 in the pre-ODI stage and 3.35 in the post-ODI stage. In the Control Group, the overall mean scores were 3.2 in pre-ODI and 3.37 in post-ODI.

e) Fit to Organization

Fit to the organization was measured with four items. In the experimental group, the overall mean score on "fit to the organization" was 2.95 in the pre-ODI stage and 3.43 in the post-ODI stage. In the Control Group, the overall mean scores were 3 in the pre-ODI stage and 3.21 in the post-ODI stage.

f) Link to Organization

Link to the organization was measured with four items. In the experimental group, the overall mean score on "link to the organization" was 2.88 in the pre-ODI stage and 3.2 in the post-ODI stage. In the Control Group, the overall mean scores were 2.86 in the pre-ODI stage and 3.1 in the post-ODI stage.

D. Interpretation of The Data - Hypothesis Testing

• Hypothesis 1

The researcher used Spearman's test to examine the relationship between OCB and organizational embeddedness, and the results showed in Table 2.

Significant(P)	Organizational Embeddedness	OCB	Correlation Coefficient	Organizational Embeddedness	OCB
OCB	0.036		OCB	0.741	
Organizational Embeddedness		0.036	Organizational Embeddedness		0.741

Table 2: Spearman's Test for OCB and Organizational Embeddedness

From the table, we can see that $p=0.036 < 0.05$, the correlation coefficient $r=0.741 > 0.5$, so OCB and organizational embeddedness were positively and strongly correlated. And OCB and turnover intention were negatively and strongly correlated. So, H_{10} is rejected, and H_{1a} is

accepted: *There is a statistically significant relationship between OCB and organizational embeddedness.*

• Hypothesis 2

The researcher used Wilcoxon signed-rank test to validate hypothesis 2. The results are shown in Table 3 and Table 4.

	Negative Ranks	Sum of Negative Ranks	Positive Ranks	Sum of Positive Ranks	Z	Asymp. Sig.
Post-ODI						
-	2	12	12	93	-2.592	0.01
Pre-ODI						

Table 3: Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Results of Experimental Group

It can be seen from the results that there are 12 items whose scores after intervention are higher than those before the intervention, and the sum of positive ranks is 93. In comparison, 2 items that score after intervention are lower than before, and the sum of negative ranks is 12. The other 10 items scored the same before and after the intervention. Check the critical value table of the Wilcoxon signed rank-sum test, $T_{min}(T+, T-)=12 < T=81$. It also can be seen from

the results that $z=-2.592$, based on a negative rank, is an asymptotic significance $p=0.01 < 0.05$. Therefore, the participants' scores after the intervention are believed to be significantly different from those before the intervention. And from the comparison of the mean before and after the intervention, it can be seen that after the intervention, the participants' scores have improved, which means that their OCB and organizational embeddedness level are improved.

	Negative Ranks	Sum of Negative Ranks	Positive Ranks	Sum of Positive Ranks	Z	Asymp. Sig.
Post-ODI						
-	2	12	9	54	-2.111	0.035
Pre-ODI						

Table 4: Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Results of Control Group

It can be seen from the results that there are 9 items whose scores after intervention are higher than those before the intervention, with the sum of positive ranks being 54, 2 items whose scores after intervention are lower than those before the intervention, with the sum of negative ranks is 12, and the other 13 items' scores are the same before and after the intervention. Check the critical value table of the Wilcoxon signed rank-sum test, $T_{min}(T+, T-)=12 < T=81$. It also can be seen from the results that $z=-2.111$, which is based on a negative rank, and asymptotic significance $p=0.035 < 0.05$. Therefore, there has been a change in participant scores before and after the intervention. Similar to the experimental group, the participants' scores have improved. But compared to the experimental group, more

items remained unchanged in the control group. Even though the scores of both the experimental and control group increased, the experimental group had more positive items, and the intervention effect was more pronounced. Thus, the researcher concludes that there is a significant change in the level of OCB and organizational embeddedness before and after the intervention for both experimental and control groups of participants. The level of OCB and organizational embeddedness increased significantly. In contrast, the level of turnover intention decreased significantly. So, H_{20} is rejected, and H_{2a} is accepted: *There is a statistically significant relationship between OCB and organizational embeddedness before and after ODI.*

• Hypothesis 3

The researcher used Spearman's Test and the Mann-Whitney U test. Through Spearman's test, the result shows that OCB and organizational embeddedness were positively and strongly correlated. And the Mann-Whitney U test's result is shown in Table 5 and Table 6.

From Table 5, we can see that the OCB $p=0.163 > 0.05$ and the organizational embeddedness

$p=0.916 > 0.05$, so the OCB and organizational embeddedness levels in the two groups have no significant differences in the pre-ODI stage.

From Table 6, we can see that the OCB $p=0.045 < 0.05$ and the organizational embeddedness $p=0.027 < 0.05$, so the OCB and organizational embeddedness levels in the two groups have significant differences in the post-ODI stage.

	Experimental Group (N)	Sum of Ranks	Control Group (N)	Sum of Ranks	Asymp. Sig.
OCB	16	227	16	301	0.163
Organizational Embeddedness	8	69	8	67	0.916

Table 5: Mann-Whitney U Test for OCB and organizational embeddedness in the pre-ODI stage

	Experimental Group (N)	Sum of Ranks	Control Group (N)	Sum of Ranks	Asymp. Sig.
OCB	16	211	16	317	0.045
Organizational Embeddedness	8	47	8	89	0.027

Table 6: Mann-Whitney U Test for OCB and organizational embeddedness in the post-ODI stage

So, H_{30} is rejected, and H_{3a} is accepted: *The OCB has a statistically significant impact on organizational embeddedness.*

E. Findings

First, the participants in this study are all school students, half of whom have no work experience, and the others have only temporary work experience. Therefore, it is challenging to observe turnover intentions directly. By analyzing the literature, according to job embeddedness theory & field theory, organizational embeddedness is significantly and negatively related to turnover intentions, and when organizational embeddedness increases, turnover intentions significantly decrease, so changes in turnover intention can also be reflected by observing organizational embeddedness. From the results of Spearman's Test, OCB and organizational embeddedness are positively and strongly correlated. So, researcher conclude that OCB and turnover intention are negatively and strongly correlated.

Second, from the quantitative analysis results, the researcher found that OCB increased in both the experimental and control groups. Therefore, it was proved that both ODI and BP original courses significantly improved students' OCB levels. However, the OCB level improvement rate of students who have undergone ODI is about 0.7% higher than that of ordinary courses. Therefore, ODI has a better effect on improving students' OCB levels than BP's original courses. To verify the results of the quantitative analysis, the researcher also conducted group interviews with the participants. In the interviews during the pre-ODI stage, both in the control group and experimental group, many participants believed that they had a certain level of OCB and could make contributions to the current organization, the class, such as winning in competitions, expanding the influence of the class by participating in activities, etc. However, according to the questions in the questionnaire, the answers of the participants in the three aspects of conscientiousness, sportsmanship, and civic virtue

were not satisfactory, mainly because they could not accurately understand relevant concepts, paid more attention to personal interests, regarded personal interests as more important than organizational interests, had double standards for colleagues and themselves, paid too much attention to internal shortcomings of the organization and did not seriously participate in organizational meetings. Participants tend to focus on personal issues such as salaries and office conditions when discussing future jobs rather than the organization's link and integration. In Post-ODI stage, during the interviews of the experimental group, the researcher found that the participants had a more accurate understanding of the concept of OCB, was more concerned about the organization, was willing to make more efforts for the excellent development of the organization, and was more concerned about others' evaluation of their organization and the positive aspects of the organization's development process. When discussing the future job, the participants' focus is not only on the salary but also on hopes of achieving a good link between the organization and themselves. In contrast, in the Post-ODI stage, the researcher found that the participants' concept of OCB was still vague in the interviews of the control group, which was related to the lack of introduction to the concept of OCB in traditional courses. At the same time, due to the introduction of students' employment concepts in traditional courses, the participants' attitudes towards OCB also changed to some extent in the interviews. For example, they no longer only pay attention to salaries and working conditions but also pay attention to the matching between individual and organization, contributions to the organization, etc. However, similar to the results of quantitative analysis, the improvement of the OCB level of participants in traditional courses is not as good as that of ODIs.

Third, the researcher used the Mann-Whitney U test to examine the relationship between OCB and organizational embeddedness in pre-and Post-ODI stages. In the Pre-ODI stage, the OCB and organizational embeddedness levels in the two groups are not significantly different, and the OCB and organizational embeddedness levels in the two groups are quite different in the post-ODI stage. As mentioned above, organizational embeddedness is significantly and negatively related to turnover intentions. Researcher conclude that the two groups' OCB and turnover intention levels are not very different in the pre-ODI stage and have significant differences in the post-ODI stage.

V. DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study is to enhance students' OCB through organizational development intervention (ODI) on sophomore of BP, thereby reducing participants' turnover intention and reducing future students' turnover rate within the first six months of employment. After an organizational development intervention (ODI), participants' OCB and organizational identification levels went up, and they were less likely to leave their jobs. The researcher gives his findings quantitatively and verifies the conclusions through group interviews. Most of the participants said that compared with pre-ODI, their sense of willingness to engage in OCB and organizational embeddedness had improved. At the same time, it can be assumed that participants' turnover intention has decreased. They focused more on the positives of the organization than on paychecks and negatives or leaving for paychecks alone.

Based on the quantitative analysis results in this study, the researcher draws the following conclusions.

After the implementation of the designed ODI, the organizational embeddedness of the participants has increased, and it can also be considered that the turnover intention has decreased.

The results of the quantitative analysis showed that the intervention program for BP students successfully created positive changes in the participants. These positive changes are manifested in a shift in mindset or perspective. Interactive lecturing, soft skills training, role-playing, and group discussions as OD tools were found to be effective and suitable for these participants. These interventions improved the mean score of organizational embeddedness. Such results are also consistent with those of qualitative studies.

Researcher have shown that the level of organizational adaptation of new employees is a nonlinear development pattern of fast first and then slow, especially the first six months of entering the company is a critical period to promote successful organizational adaptation^[30]. However, interviews with HR managers in the organization found that new employees often have a high turnover rate due to incompatibility with the organizational system, code of conduct, and organizational culture within the first six months of entering the organization. In response to such problems, the human resources department promotes new employees' adaptation through induction training. It lets new employees integrate into the organization more quickly through training activities. However, considering the current social environment in China and the personality characteristics of individual employees, it is impossible to fundamentally solve the problem of the high turnover rate of new employees through induction training alone. Therefore, as the last stop before an employee enters an organization, colleges, significantly higher vocational colleges, bear essential responsibilities. Colleges should improve the organizational embeddedness of students in various ways to reduce the possible turnover behavior or turnover intention after entering the organization. Based on the embeddedness theory, numerous researchers commonly use fit to the organization, link to the organization, and sacrifice to measure the level of the organizational embeddedness. The hardest of these three things to simulate in college is sacrifice, so it can only be explained, not accurately measured.

Through the above analyses, the researcher obtains the model of this study, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: The researcher developed OCB-Turnover Intention Model

This is a 2 by 2 model, with the X-axis representing turnover intentions and the Y-axis representing OCB levels. The researcher divided the strategy into four areas, from I to IV.

In Area I, the OCB level is low, and the turnover intention is high, so the result must be turnover behavior. The researcher tries to keep the intervention object far away from this area as an OD intervenor.

The turnover intention is high in Area II, where the OCB level is high. Combined with the job embeddedness theory, employees exhibit poor fit to the organization. According to the traditional understanding, when the employees' OCB level is high, there is better organizational embeddedness, and the turnover intention decreases. However, this study found that even though the OCB level of some participants had improved, due to the mismatch between their values and organizational culture, even if the participants had a high level of OCB, they still could not fit into the organization, leading to a decrease of participants' organizational embeddedness and an increase in their turnover intention. As an OD intervenor, the researcher should build a bridge in time so that the values and cultures of the intervention object and the organization converge, improve the organizational embeddedness of the intervention object, and thus reduce the turnover intention.

In Area III, the OCB level is high, and the turnover intention is low. This region is optimal and is the target of this study. From the perspective of the OD intervenor, if the OCB level of the intervention object is increased and the turnover intention is decreased, then they will work stably

and efficiently in the organization, bringing benefits to all stakeholders.

In Area IV, the OCB level is low, and the turnover intention is low. With the same in Area II, employees exhibit poor links to the organization. In this study, the researcher found that some participants in the control group just did their own thing and didn't care about the organization's development. There is also a reluctance to participate in any kind of working group and not to communicate too much with members of the organization. Through qualitative and quantitative analysis of the data collected by the control group, the researcher found that these participants are in area IV, and their links to the organization are low. Through interviews, the researcher learned that human resources departments have similar findings. Almost all companies have such employees. They are neither willing to do anything in the organization that is not their job nor to leave it. In China, a particular word to describe it is "Tang Ping," meaning lie flat. An OD intervenor, through intervention, members can increase communication with other members of the organization, and by participating in different working groups, establish connections with various members of the organization, and then increase the degree of the link to the organization.

Based on the above analysis, the researcher further discusses with the human resource department in the organization, and combined with the basic situation of dissatisfaction with the organization proposed by Albert O. Hirschman in 1970^[31], the researcher further inferred Figure 2 to deduce the four kinds of employees with different performances in the organizations, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: The Researcher Developed Four Kinds of Employees Strategy

In this model, if employees are in Area I, then such employees have lower OCB levels and higher turnover intentions, and such employees will have turnover behavior and leave the organization. Such employees should be attended to and intervened promptly in an effort to improve their OCB while allowing them to understand and identify with the culture and values of the organization. This will help improve the OCB level of employees, reduce their turnover intention, and thus avoid turnover behavior.

If the employee is in Area II, the OCB level of such employees is higher. According to psychological contract theory, this kind of employee often has various OCB behavior, including voice behavior. But most of the time, their OCB is not rewarded accordingly, or their OCB does not fit the organizational culture, so their turnover intention is also high. They often express their different opinions, but usually, these opinions are difficult to be accepted by managers for various reasons. Therefore, these kinds of

employees are also prone to turnover behavior. For such employees, employers should promptly let them understand the organization's culture and values, and try their best to make them accept the organization's values, identify with the organization's culture, and keep in line with other employees in the organization in terms of thinking and behavior, to avoid conflicts with organization members caused by differences in values.

If employees are in Area III, such employees have higher OCB levels and lower turnover intentions. They have higher loyalty to the organization and are willing to contribute to the development of the organization. Such employees are the most important in every organization. Employers should make this kind of employee the key training target, on the one hand, try to improve his ability to contribute more to the organization. And they should also be shaped into the organization's "stars," play their driving effect, and influence and drive more employees so that they can have a common direction of effort.

If employees are in Area IV, their OCB level is low, and their turnover intention is also low. Such employees usually have weak ties to the organization, are unwilling to take on responsibilities outside their own jobs, and often choose to remain silent when encountering problems. As mentioned above, they are in a "Tang Ping" state. Such employees can perform their jobs, but they do not contribute much to the development of the organization. Faced with such an employee, the employer should try to improve their motivation, involve him in different working groups, increase their communication with other employees in the organization, help them find employees with the same hobbies and let them work together, and try to improve their connection with the organization so that they have a higher passion for working.

VI. LIMITATIONS AND NEEDS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

In theory, this study further expands our understanding of the relationship between Chinese higher vocational students' OCB and organizational embeddedness and turnover intention. First, when studying the OCB of higher vocational students, the particularity determined by organizational characteristics should be discussed in-depth and simulated in the school classroom. Second, clarifying what affects the OCB of higher vocational students and exploring the educational methods to improve the OCB of higher vocational students will provide a solid ground for vocational education theory studies and make up for the deficiency in the field of OCB research in China. In practice, this research findings can further improve the schools and enterprises' understanding of the relation between OCB, organizational embeddedness, and future turnover intention of vocational college students and employees. Second, enhancing the OCB of vocational college students helps to improve the level of organizational embeddedness level and reduce future turnover intention. All OCB-trained vocational college graduates should adapt to the organizational environment sooner with higher organizational embeddedness and have a low turnover intention.

Although this study has made theoretical and practical contributions to the improvement of students' OCB level, the improvement of students' organizational embeddedness, and the reduction of students' future turnover intention in higher vocational colleges, this research still has the following limitations that need to be promoted in the future study.

First, the selection of intervention subjects in this study is limited. Only 30 participants from the major of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering (MEE) were selected for OD intervention in this study. However, with 36 majors and nearly 7,000 students in BP, the proportion of participants was relatively small. Also, among the students who participated in the OD intervention in this study, there were only two females, and the rest were males. Therefore, this study did not conclude whether the female participants responded to the intervention the same way as the male participants. In addition, more than 70% of the students who received the intervention were from rural areas. Compared with students from cities, this study did not consider the differences caused by their growth environment. In future studies, the number of participants should be increased to ensure scientific proof of how interventions work.

Second, the selection of variables in the study is limited. The participants in this study were all BP students, most of whom had no work experience. Therefore, many intervention behaviors are carried out by simulating real scenarios. However, some variables, such as salaries, cannot be manipulated through scenario simulation. In addition, some variables were unrelated to student intervention, such as altruism and courtesy. The variables that can be selected in this study are relatively limited. Only 1 IV is selected, including four sub-variables: organizational Identification, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, and civic virtue; and 1 DV, including two sub-variables, fit and link to the organization. More variables, such as gender, family environment, etc., should be considered in further research. This can make the research results more scientific and reasonable.

Third, the limitation of intervention effects by comparing the quantitative analyses before and after ODI, this study found that the intervention has a particular impact, and the relevant variables of the participants improved. However, the percentage increase was lower than expected. This may have been caused by the participants' lack of work experience or the short duration of the intervention. In the future, this study should continue for about a year after students graduate to see how they do in the group.

Fourth, is the limitation of the length of research. The intervention in this study lasted 16 weeks, but it was shorter in studies involving students with no work experience. As a student with three years of education during vocational college, the intervention time should be longer to ensure the effectiveness of the intervention. At the same time, due to their age restrictions, although students accept new things quickly and can quickly show the effect of the intervention, they also update information fast and are often affected by the surrounding environment. Therefore, the impact of the intervention will disappear in a brief period. Therefore, this study should be ongoing, with uninterrupted interventions

for students in the future until they enter the organization after graduation. In this way, the effect of the intervention can be ensured. At the same time, it can be accurately observed whether the turnover rate of the participants receiving the intervention has decreased. At the same time, the intervention should be moved up to when students start vocational colleges to have the most impact.

Fifth is the limitation of using a 7-point Likert scale in the questionnaire. In the data analysis of this study, the researcher found that the results of the 5-point Likert scale were relatively concentrated and could not be well after the research, which may be related to the habits of Chinese. Therefore, it is recommended to use a 7-point scale in future studies to make the results more noticeable.

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